

Trace determination of nickel-, cadmium-, copper- and zinc(II) using rhodanine — an amperometric reagent

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Rhodanine is employed as amperometric reagent for the trace determination of metals such as Ni^{II}, Cd^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} in BR buffer at pHs 6.0, 5.5, 4.91 and 4.6, respectively, with $\mu = 0.1 M$ (KCl) and fresh 0.001% gelatin. Titration potential has been selected in the limiting region of the cathodic wave of titled metals. The statistical analysis of the observed data reveals high accuracy and precision.

p-Dimethylaminobenzylidene rhodanine has been known to be a sensitive reagent for Cu, Ag and Hg¹. Rhodanine (4-thiazolidene-2-thione) is polarographically active and shows anodic wave at dropping mercury electrode². The present paper deals with the applicability of rhodanine as an amperometric titrant for the estimation of small amounts of Cu^{II}, Cd^{II}, Zn^{II} and Ni^{II}.

Results and discussion

For amperometric estimations of titled metals experimental sets were prepared keeping known concentration of rhodanine in BR buffer at appropriate pH containing 1 ml 0.001% fresh gelatin as maximum suppressor at constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.1 M$) maintained using KCl as supporting electrolyte in 10-ml volume. The plateau potential of the metal ion applied was -0.5 , -0.9 , -1.3 and $-1.3 V$ vs

SCE for Cu^{II}, Cd^{II}, Zn^{II} and Ni^{II}, respectively. Amperometric titrations were performed in the usual way at pH 4.91, 4.60, 5.50 and 6.01 for Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Ni^{II}, respectively, by adding standard solution of the metal ion. The current was noted on multiflex galvanometer. On plotting $[(V + \nu)/V] \times i$ against volume of titrant, reverse L-shaped curves were observed. Under similar condition rhodanine solution was used as titrant resulting L-shaped curves. The results are shown in Table 1. The end-point indicated M : L ratio of 1 : 1 for Cu-L and Zn-L and 1 : 2 for Ni-L and Cd-L, which is supported by literature³.

Ultramicro and micro quantities of Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cd^{II} were determined by the proposed procedure. The amounts of metal ions in the concentration range 1.0×10^{-4} to 1×10^{-3} were detected with less than $\pm 1\%$ error, with minimum detection limit of 0.3 mg. The value of stan-

Table 1. Amperometric determination of Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Ni^{II} with rhodanine

Plateau potential : Cu^{II} = -0.5 , Zn^{II} = -1.3 , Cd^{II} = -0.9 , Ni^{II} = $-1.3 V$ vs SCE, supporting electrolyte : BR buffer, ionic strength (μ) = $0.1 M$ (KCl), pH = 4.91, 4.60, 5.50, 6.01 \pm 0.02 (respectively for Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Ni^{II}), temp. = 27°

Sl. no.	Amount of Cu ^{II}			Amount of Zn ^{II}			Amount of Cd ^{II}			Amount of Ni ^{II}		
	Taken	Found	Error %									
	mg	mg										
1.	0.3339	0.3311	-0.83	0.2938	0.2965	+0.91	0.2807	0.2831	+0.85	0.2537	0.2517	-0.78
2.	0.4092	0.4123	+0.75	0.3395	0.3369	+0.76	0.3357	0.3332	-0.74	0.3304	0.3322	+0.54
3.	0.5796	0.5761	-0.60	0.4505	0.4536	+0.68	0.4671	0.4646	-0.53	0.4602	0.4621	+0.41
4.	0.7812	0.7854	+0.53	0.5224	0.5252	+0.53	0.7299	0.7333	+0.46	0.6136	0.6168	+0.52
5.	0.9576	0.9531	-0.46	0.7183	0.7148	-0.48	0.8984	0.8943	-0.45	0.8555	0.8522	-0.38
6.	1.1781	1.1833	+0.44	0.9795	0.9827	+0.32	1.2791	1.2837	+0.35	1.1387	1.1357	-0.26
7.	1.4492	1.4442	-0.34	1.2407	1.2443	+0.29	1.4459	1.4414	-0.31	1.4753	1.4784	+0.21

standard deviation and coefficient of variance are with respect to minimum detection limit. The statistical treatment of the observed data, i.e. coefficient of variation (1.05, 0.90, 0.90, 1.38 for Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Ni^{II}, respectively) indicates that the procedure is simple, sensitive and fairly selective for estimation of titled metal ions.

Amperometric titrations were not hampered in the presence of Li⁺, Na⁺, K⁺, Cl⁻, SO₄²⁻, NO₃⁻ and CH₃COO⁻. However, Bi³⁺, Cd²⁺ and Mn²⁺ interfered seriously even if present in minute quantities.

Experimental

Electrochemical behavior of rhodanine was investigated in 0.1 M KCl, fresh 0.001% gelatin and Britton-Robinson buffer at pH 5.50 ± 0.02. Polarograms were recorded after removal of oxygen by passing a stream of purified nitrogen gas for 10 min. Well-defined anodic wave was obtained for rhodanine with $E^{1/2} - 0.24$ V vs SCE.

A manually operated polarograph with Tinsley potentiometer and a multiflex galvanometer (sens. 8.10×10^{-9} A/div.) were used. Dropping mercury electrode (d.m.e) with capillary characteristics of $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.214 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{1/2}$ at 40 cm effective height of mercury column was used as an indicator electrode. A calomel electrode was used as reference electrode. An Elico LI 120 pH meter was used. Double-distilled mercury was used throughout. The test solution was deaerated by bubbling purified nitrogen gas before titrations for 5 min. All titrations were performed at room tempera-

ture. All the chemicals used were of extra pure grade. Stock solutions of the metals (0.01 M) were prepared in double-distilled water and standardized⁴. Fresh solution of rhodanine was prepared in double-distilled water. Titrations of the titled metals were performed in potassium chloride ($\mu = 0.1$ M) and buffer of suitable pH. Britton-Robinson buffer was prepared⁵ from glacial acetic acid, boric acid, phosphoric acid and sodium hydroxide.

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